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Proteasome subunit-specific activation in p53 mutant cancer in humans.

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We describe here an essential subunit-specific addiction-like induction of genes encoding the proteasome in human cancer. Expression of a p53 point mutant in human cells transiently was sufficient to induce expression of a specific collection of proteasome genes. A proteasome profile representing the same collection of proteasome subunits was observed in the primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer. These genes included PSMA4 and PSMA6, PSMD10 and PSMD12, and PDME3. This collection of genes may represent a core dependency on the proteasome in cancer found immediately after transformation begins and in the tumor at clinical presentation.